

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Parent–infant interaction trajectories in infants with an elevated likelihood for autism in relation to 3-year clinical outcome

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Abstract

Developmental antecedents of autism may affect parent–infant interactions (PII), altering the context in which core social skills develop. While studies have identified differences in PII between infants with and without elevated likelihood (EL) for autism, samples have been small. Here, we examined whether previously reported differences are replicable. From a longitudinal study of 113 EL and 27 typical likelihood infants (TL), 6-min videotaped unstructured PII was blind rated at 8 and 14 months on eight interactional qualities. Autism outcome was assessed at 36 months. Linear mixed-effects models found higher parent sensitive responsiveness, nondirectiveness, and mutuality ratings in TL than EL infants with and without later autism. PII qualities at 8 (infant positive affect, parent directiveness) and 14 months (infant attentiveness to parent, mutuality) predicted 3-year autism. Attentiveness to parent decreased between 8 and 14 months in EL infants with later autism. This larger study supports previous findings of emerging alterations in PII in this group and extends on this by detecting earlier (8-month) predictive effects of PII for autism outcome and a more marked trajectory of decreased social attentiveness. The findings strengthen the evidence base to support the implementation of early preemptive interventions to support PII in infants with early autism signs.

Lay Summary

Previous studies have found parent–infant interaction (PII) differences between infants with elevated likelihood (EL) and with typical likelihood (TL) for autism. This may be due to early changes in social communication skills. However, sample sizes have been small. Here, we investigated whether we could replicate previous findings including a new larger sample by looking at whether infants at EL differed from infants at TL in PII qualities at 8 and 14 months, and whether these qualities differed in those with from those without autism diagnosis at 3 years.

The members of BASIS Team are displayed in the 'Acknowledgements'.

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This study found that the TL group was rated to have more mutual play and parents played with their infant more sensitively and less directly than the EL group (infants with and without later autism). PII qualities at 8 (infant positivity, parent directiveness) and 14 months (infant interest in parent, mutual play) differed between those with and without later autism. Between 8 and 14 months, the baby's interest in the parent during play reduced faster in infants with later autism. As well as showing similar results to previous research, the larger sample has allowed us to find earlier interactional differences (8 months) and developmental changes in social attention that statistically predict a later autism diagnosis. The study highlights the importance of supporting PII in parents of EL infants in the first year of life.

KEYWORDS

autism spectrum disorders, elevated likelihood of autism, infant siblings, longitudinal, mother–infant, parent–child interaction, social attention

INTRODUCTION

Social experiences begin within the family environment when infant interactions with their parents are a central aspect of social development. In the context of emerging autism, early precursors are hypothesized to bidirectionally affect the nature of infant and parent interactive behavior (Dawson, 2008). As hypothesized within the transactional model of development, early subtle differences in infant's social competence may alter parental responses toward the infant and subsequent mutuality in parent–infant interaction (PII), further amplifying autism-related symptoms with cascading effects on later development (Sameroff, 2009). Studies have employed an infant sibling design to study PII between infants with an elevated likelihood (EL, infants who have an older autistic sibling) and those with typical likelihood (TL, infants who have an older neurotypically developing sibling) of autism, as the former are more likely to develop autism (approximately 18.7%) compared with neurotypically developing infants (Ozonoff et al., 2011). These studies reveal altered PII in the second half of the first year, reporting EL and TL group differences predominantly in preverbal interactive behaviors (Campbell et al., 2015; Paul et al., 2011; Pijl et al., 2021; Wan et al., 2019). These differences have motivated parent-mediated interventions, which have shown some efficacy in supporting early social communication development in infants with a family history of autism (Green et al., 2017; Whitehouse et al., 2021).

In one of the earliest PII studies, Wan et al. (2012, 2013) evaluated both parent and infant qualities of PII in relation to 3-year autism outcome. At around 7 months of age, EL infants were less lively, while their parents were less sensitively responsive and nondirective (fewer congruent/prompt responses to infant's behavior and less likely to follow the infant's lead), compared with the TL group. These parental differences remained at 14 months while differences in dyadic engagement intensity also emerged. Importantly, among the EL group, 14-month

infant positivity, attentiveness to parent and dyadic mutuality (the amount and degree of sharedness and reciprocity in PII) significantly predicted 3-year autism outcome independent of concurrent early autism signs. In this sample, parental behaviors did not predict autism outcome. Several subsequent studies have also reported fewer infant socio-communicative behaviors within PII in EL-autism infants, detectable in the latter half of the first year, including fewer gestures and gesture-speech combinations (EL: $n = 55$, Choi et al., 2019), initiating fewer gestures (EL: $n = 35$, Campbell et al., 2015), and less responsiveness to their mother's bids (EL: $n = 104$, Kellerman et al., 2020) relative to no-autism EL infants. Pijl et al. (2021) also found that EL infants ($n = 101$) show fewer infant initiations at 10 months than TL controls but did not follow up to autism outcome. Such communication differences in gesture and vocalizations persisted at 18 months in EL and EL-autism infants (EL n s ranging between 12 and 50, Leezenbaum et al., 2014; Paradé & Iverson, 2015; Winder et al., 2013). These differences in social communication behavior during naturalistic interaction could have cascading effects on social learning and subsequent development.

Evidence for differences in parental behavior is more limited. Addressing this question is important, because parent-mediated interventions are designed to work through parent behavior in supporting development. Two studies found that parents of EL infants compared with parents of TL infants tended to use more touch and verbal requests to elicit infants' response and attention from 9 to 15 months (EL: $n = 16$, Srinivasan & Bhat, 2020) and highly directive parental behavior predicted slower growth in infants' parent-directed smiles from 9 to 18 months (EL: $n = 30$, Harker et al., 2016). These studies did not follow EL infants up to autism outcome. Directiveness may also be adaptive to infant behaviors; for example, parents of infants at EL intensify their prosodic expressions (infant-directed speech) from 12 to 18 months compared with parents of TL infants (Quigley et al., 2016). Nevertheless, other studies, mostly

with smaller samples, suggest no EL and TL group differences in parental directiveness or other social behaviors and no associations between parent behavior and later autism outcome (Campbell et al., 2015; Del Rosario et al., 2023; Leezenbaum et al., 2014; Schwichtenberg et al., 2019).

Although studies have made a great effort in delineating PII in infants at EL, progress in understanding the role of PII in the EL context has been hampered by small samples and/or the heterogeneity of PII variables. Intensive resources required to recruit and conduct PII measures with EL and TL samples, and sample attrition in longitudinal sibling studies, mean that EL-autism subsamples are typically likely underpowered to capture PII differences. A notable exception is Kellerman et al. (2020) who studied the microanalytic features of dyadic synchrony, maternal responsiveness, and infant responsiveness of PII in 104 EL and 71 TL infants at 6, 9, and 12 months of age. Responsiveness and synchrony group differences were evident by 12 months of age, but not earlier. However, the microanalytic approach was limited by a focus on a very specific narrow range of behaviors (for example, maternal responsiveness was measured by combining the frequency of infant-led gazes to mother and object, positive affect, and vocalization). While valuable, qualitative components (for example, how sensitive the responses are) that may be critical for social development, require evaluating a broader range of behaviors (Morawska et al., 2015; Wan et al., 2017). The present study adds to the field by representing the largest study to date of qualitative components of PII in EL infants ($n = 113$) at 8 and 14 months and following up to 3-year autism outcome. It utilizes the same methodology as Wan et al. (2013), but on a separate cohort sample—thus providing a strong replicability test for the original findings. Examining the replicability of previously reported effects including a larger independent sample was one of our main goals and represents a core principle of open science, important for the improvement of the reliability of research findings (Nosek et al., 2022).

Based on Wan et al.'s (2013) findings, we tested for differences between EL (EL-autism/EL-no autism) and TL infants in PII qualities in parent domains (sensitive responsiveness and nondirectiveness) and infant liveliness at 8 months. Considering the significance of early PII quality for the development of children's social functioning, we also predicted from previous work that PII differences would increase between 8 and 14 months with more areas of interaction affected at 14 months (both parent domains, infant attentiveness to parent, infant positive affect, dyadic mutuality, and engagement intensity). Finally, based on Wan et al. (2013), we tested whether differences between the EL and TL groups (particularly in infant positive affect, infant attentiveness, and dyadic mutuality) at 14 months would relate to later autism.

METHODS

Participants

A total of 143 parent–infant dyads came from a UK prospective study of infants who had an older sibling with autism and for whom PII (at least one time point; see analysis for more information) and autism outcome data were available (The British Autism Study of Infant Siblings (BASIS): www.basisnetwork.org; Phase 2 data collection; ethical approval: UK National Health Service National Research Ethics Service London reference number: 06/MRE/02/73). Of the 143 children, three were excluded from this study because they were absent from the 36-month assessment. The final sample consisted of 113 infants (64 male; 52 female) with an older sibling with a community clinical diagnosis of autism (EL group) and 27 infants (14 male; 13 female) with at least one older sibling (TL group). Informed consent was given by one or both parents. Confirmation of EL status and criteria for inclusion are described in more detail in the [Supplementary Materials](#).

Measures

All measures (except autism outcome) were taken at 8- and 14-month research lab visits. The measures employed in this paper were largely motivated by Wan et al.'s (2013) study to enhance comparability.

Parent–infant interaction

Assessment of PII mirrored the PII assessment conducted by Wan et al. (2013); same measure and location. The Manchester Assessment of Caregiver–Infant Interaction (MACI; version 2.2; Wan et al., 2017) evaluates global aspects of interaction between the primary caregiver and the infant on 8 seven-point scales from observation of 6-min unstructured play video recorded after a period of familiarization. The parent sits on a play mat with a small set of selected toys and is instructed to play with their infant as they would normally do at home, with or without the use of toys as they prefer. A standard small set of toys was offered, broadly suitable for infants' developmental level, such as a rattle, a soft book, soft toys, and a stacking toy. The MACI scales evaluate parental behaviors (sensitive responsiveness and nondirectiveness), infant behaviors (attentiveness to caregiver, positive affect, negative affect, and liveliness), and dyadic qualities (mutuality and engagement intensity). The videos were rated by fully trained and reliable coders, blinded to all participant information. Coders completed a full MACI training comprising a 3-day workshop, practice codings (three practice sets), personalized feedback after each set, and a thorough two-part reliability

assessment in which high inter-rater agreement was established. For the current study, ongoing evaluation of coding (on a proportion of clips) was undertaken to examine coding agreement between raters. Possible discrepancies in the ratings were resolved by re-reviewing the clips and by mutual agreement. The 10% of PII clips at each time point were independently blind-coded and further tested for inter-rater agreement through single measures intra-class correlations using a two-way mixed effects model based on absolute agreement definition. The MACI has demonstrated good to excellent psychometric characteristics and inter-rater reliability (IRR; see [Supplementary Materials](#) for IRR for the current study) and has previously differentiated infants at EL from those at TL (Wan et al., 2012, 2013) and been sensitive to the effects of intervention in EL children (Green et al., 2015, 2017; Whitehouse et al., 2019).

Developmental level

The Mullen Scales of Early Learning (MSEL, Mullen, 1995) is a standardized assessment of cognitive capacity and motor development for children of 0–68 months administered by an experimenter, and consists of five domains: expressive language, receptive language, visual reception, gross motor skill, and fine motor skill. The scores of these areas (excluding gross motor skills) were combined to produce an Early Learning Composite (ELC) standard score (mean = 100, SD = 15).

Adaptive functioning

The Vineland Adaptive Behavior Scales—second edition (VABS-II, Sparrow et al., 2005) is a parent-report semi-structured questionnaire measure of daily adaptive behavior incorporating four main domains: communication, daily living skills, socialization, and motor skills, combined to yield an Adaptive Behavior Composite score (ABC) (mean = 100, SD = 15), a standardized measure of general adaptive behavior. Lower scores indicate greater difficulties in adaptive behavior.

Early autism signs

The Autism Observation Scale for Infants (AOSI; Bryson et al., 2008), a 19-item observational measure of early autism signs, was administered at the 8- and 14-month visits. The AOSI consists of standard semi-structured tasks led by an examiner while the infant sits on the parent's lap. Assessment of early autism signs includes particular behaviors (eye contact, atypical motor and sensory behavior, response to name, imitation, reciprocity, differential response to facial emotion, tracking and

attentional disengagement, and social-communicative behaviors) and scores on these behaviors are summed to yield an overall score.

Assessment of autism outcome at 3 years

Of the 113 infants at EL, 17 (15%) met criteria for an autism diagnosis, 64 (56.6%) were categorized as typically developing, and 32 (28.3%) were categorized as developing atypically but not with an autism diagnosis at 36 months, based on a battery of clinical assessments by an independent team to establish clinical outcome. Autism diagnosis was estimated based on, among other measures, 24- and 36-month results from assessments using the 'Autism Diagnostic Observation Schedule-Generic (ADOS-G)—Second Edition' (Lord et al., 2012), the 'Autism Diagnostic Interview—Revised (ADI-R)' (Rutter et al., 2003), The Social Responsiveness Scale (SRS; Constantino & Gruber, 2012), and the Quantitative Checklist for Autism in Toddlers (Q-CHAT). This procedure was used as it involved all the available clinical data across time points to be considered by experienced researchers/clinicians. More details on clinical assessment can be found in the [Supplementary Materials](#).

Analyses

At 8 months, $N = 16$ had missing data (no clip: $n = 10$; technical issues: $n = 6$), and at 14 months, $N = 10$ had missing data (no clip: $n = 6$; technical issues: $n = 4$). All participants were included because they had at least one PII score at 8 or 14 months and the statistical method used can handle missing data and unbalanced designs well (see below). Before the main analyses, the internal characteristics between the MACI scales were examined at each time point and the PII variables were inspected for distribution normality, linearity, and extreme cases (refer to the [Supplementary Materials](#) for details).

Testing differences in PII by autism outcome status

Linear mixed effects models were performed to examine differences in PII by 3-year autism outcome status (developmental groups: EL-autism, EL-no autism, TL) across 8 and 14 months of age. Each PII item was included in a separate model as the dependent variable. Participant was included as a random intercept to account for individual variability at the baseline. Fixed effects of the developmental groups, age (to adjust for variability in age, actual age in months was included: 6–11 and 11–18 months), their interaction, as well as the effect of gender were tested by comparing the fit of a series of

successive models against a null model with the likelihood ratio test (LRT) (see [Supplementary Materials](#)). Linear mixed effects models were performed after selecting the best-fitting model using LRTs (see [Supplementary Materials](#)). Given that a portion of the sample ($n = 28$) had received parent-mediated intervention at 14 months (Green et al., 2015), supplementary analysis was run including ‘intervention’ as a further categorical predictor/control variable (those undergone intervention compared to the rest of the sample) in the models that showed group and age or group by age effects in PII. To adjust for multiple comparisons in the main analysis, false discovery rate (FDR) correction was applied, which controls for the proportion of incorrect rejection of null hypotheses (Benjamini & Hochberg, 1995). The ‘lmer’ function within the ‘lme4’ package in R was used (Bates et al., 2014).

Testing PII as a predictor of autism outcome

In line with Wan et al. (2013), supplementary analysis was performed to further elucidate whether the PII aspects were significant predictors of 36-month autism outcome. Thus, the PII items in which a developmental group or developmental group by age effect was shown (adjusting for age and gender) were tested in relation to autism outcome (no autism outcome: EL-no autism and TL infants/autism outcome: EL-autism infants) using binomial logistic regression separately at 8 and 14 months. As PII variables intercorrelate statistically and conceptually, each PII item was analyzed in a separate model, adjusting for infant age and AOSI. Hierarchical regression models were employed: the PII item was entered first, age was added second, and AOSI last to control for the variability each accounted for in autism outcome in addition to PII. The decision to control for the effect of AOSI was made to maintain the consistency with the study replicated and considering that autism-related symptoms may have an amplifying effect within PII over developmental time, as theorized by the transactional model of development. Thus, although we acknowledge that controlling for AOSI is likely to hide some real differences in PII between groups, any such effects in PII qualities should not simply be reflecting behavioral signs. In addition, the hierarchical approach followed in binomial logistic regressions allowed the examination of the variance each PII variable accounted for in ASD outcome separately (without adjusting for AOSI and in addition to AOSI). Following the analytical procedure by Wan et al. (2013), the regressions were performed again including MSEL as a further covariate to consider or partial out the possibility that effects are due to general developmental delay. The statistical package IBM® SPSS® version 27 was used for this analysis. Data were screened for influential cases, linearity of the logit, and multicollinearity (see [Supplementary Materials](#) for details).

Community involvement

There was no specific community input from autistic individuals or family members for this study. However, the BASIS-STAAARS network considers families as partners in our research program. We have a parent consultation group where we organize regular meetings to discuss targeted ethical, procedural, and strategic issues at all stages of our work. In 2019, we held a family ‘expo’ event including parents (some of whom had an autism diagnosis), older siblings with an autism diagnosis, and some of the infant siblings who were in mid-childhood, both to share our findings and to gain feedback on our proposed new studies. As part of our work in AIMS-2-TRIALS, we lead regular online meetings of the ethics and biomarkers working groups in which autistic people help us shape the directions of our research.

RESULTS

Participant demographic characteristics

Infant demographic characteristics for both time points are presented in detail in Table 1 (specific data on socioeconomic status and race/ethnicity were not recorded). Overall, the mean infant age was $M = 8.70$ ($SD = 0.84$) at the 8 month assessment and $M = 14.95$ ($SD = 0.94$) at the 14 month assessment. Table 1 presents infant demographic characteristics and developmental outcomes by ASD outcome status at each assessment. Groups differed in biological sex, AOSI at both time points, and MSEL and VABS at 14 months.

Group and time effects of parent–infant interaction at 8 and 14 months

Table 2 provides detailed statistics of the linear mixed effects model analyses between the TL, EL-no autism, and EL-autism outcome groups. Figure 1 provides a depiction of the significant effects. Regarding the parent MACI scales, a significant effect of the developmental group (sensitive responsiveness: $F(2, 129.38) = 5.72$, $p = 0.004$, $\eta^2 = 0.08$; nondirectiveness: $F(2, 132.03) = 10.80$, $p < 0.001$, $\eta^2 = 0.14$) and age (sensitive responsiveness: $F(1, 136.64) = 34.75$, $p < 0.001$, $\eta^2 = 0.20$; nondirectiveness: $F(1, 140.73) = 7.06$, $p = 0.008$, $\eta^2 = 0.05$) was found. These PII ratings increased from 8 to 14 months, and FDR-adjusted post hoc comparisons revealed that TL ratings in parent sensitive responsiveness were higher compared with EL-no autism ($p = 0.02$) and EL-autism group ($p = 0.004$). However, no sensitive responsiveness differences between EL groups were found ($p = 0.07$). In contrast, nondirectiveness showed a graded effect; while the TL group similarly received the highest nondirectiveness ratings (vs. EL-no autism: $p = 0.001$;

TABLE 1 Participant characteristics by autism outcome status at 8 and 14 months.

	8 months					14 months				
	Group mean (SD)		EL-autism (N = 17)	$F\chi^2$	η^2	Group mean (SD)		EL-autism (N = 17)	$F\chi^2$	η^2
TL (N = 27)	EL-no autism (N = 96)	TL (N = 27)				EL-no autism (N = 96)				
Age in months	8.89 (0.89)	8.67 (0.83)	8.59 (0.80)	0.91	0.01	15.11 (0.89)	14.92 (0.95)	14.88 (0.99)	0.50	0.01
Sex M/F	14/13	48/48	15/2	8.67 ^{f,*}	0.25 ^e	-	-	-	-	-
MSEL ELC	112.48 (13.36)	107.54 (15.13)	101.82 (16.70)	2.68 ^{***}	0.04	102.56 (14.43)	95.95 (14.13) ^a	85.53 (12.81)	7.68 ^{h,**}	0.10
VABS ABC	98.69 (10.72) ^b	94.62 (11.73) ^b	90.65 (14.57)	2.42 ^{***}	0.04	101.37 (11.68)	97.26 (12.13) ^c	89.63 (8.63) ^b	5.07 ^{i,**}	0.07
AOSI total ^c	5.26 (3.13)	8.74 (4.62)	10.24 (4.76)	12.81 ^{d,g,**}	0.11	4.07 (3.52)	5.86 (4.40) ^b	9.47 (5.23)	8.07 ^{h,**}	0.11

Abbreviations: AOSI, Autism Observation Scale for Infants; EL, elevated likelihood; MSEL ELC, Mullen Scales of Early Learning Early Learning Composite; TL, typical likelihood; VABS, Vineland Adaptive Behavior Scales; χ^2 , Chi-square statistic; η^2 , Eta-squared, measure of effect size.

^aN = 2 missing.

^bN = 1 missing.

^cN = 3 missing.

^dWelch's *F* ratio is reported because homogeneity of variance was not met.

^eCramer's *V* statistic was used as a measure of effect size.

^fMales were over-represented in the EL-autism group.

^gSignificant difference in the TL compared to the other two groups.

^hSignificant difference in the EL-autism compared to the other two groups.

ⁱSignificant difference between the TL and EL-autism group.

* $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$.

vs. EL-autism group: $p < 0.0001$), the EL-no autism group also showed higher nondirectiveness than the EL-autism group ($p = 0.02$).

Concerning the infant MACI scales, infant attentiveness to parent showed a significant increase in scores with age ($F(1, 132.24) = 5.94, p = 0.02, \eta^2 = 0.04$), as well as a marginally significant effect of developmental group ($F(2, 156.72) = 2.95, p = 0.06, \eta^2 = 0.04$). The highest ratings were shown in the TL group and the lowest in the EL-autism group based on FDR correction for multiple comparisons, though the results were nonsignificant ($ps > 0.44$). However, the age by developmental group interaction was significant ($F(2, 133.81) = 4.19, p = 0.02, \eta^2 = 0.06$), as TL infants showed increasing attentiveness to parent from 8 and 14 months, as EL infants showed decreasing scores. In addition, there was a significant effect of developmental group ($F(2, 158.41) = 3.93, p = 0.02, \eta^2 = 0.05$) and age ($F(1, 136.24) = 6.90, p = 0.009, \eta^2 = 0.05$) on positive affect. Pairwise comparisons using FDR showed higher positive affect scores in the EL groups compared to the TL group but the results were nonsignificant ($ps > 0.09$). Furthermore, there was a significant effect of age ($F(1, 149.27) = 95.65, p < 0.001, \eta^2 = 0.39$) on liveliness.

In the dyadic scales, a significant effect of developmental group ($F(2, 128.08) = 8.71, p < 0.001, \eta^2 = 0.12$) and age ($F(1, 139.89) = 13.77, p < 0.001, \eta^2 = 0.09$) on mutuality was found. FDR-adjusted post hoc comparisons indicated higher mutuality in the TL group compared to EL-no autism ($p < 0.001$) and EL-autism

groups ($p < 0.001$), while the EL-no autism and EL-autism groups did not differ ($p = 0.17$). Finally, only a significant effect of age ($F(1, 152.47) = 23.29, p < 0.001, \eta^2 = 0.13$) on engagement intensity was shown.

In the supplementary analysis including 'intervention' as a further covariate, the results remained the same, except for dyadic mutuality, where 'intervention' emerged as a significant predictor in the model ($B = -0.72, p = 0.003$). This was not surprising, as there are likely to be differences in infants enrolled in the intervention per se compared to the rest of the sample. However, the effect of age and autism likelihood group on mutuality remained significant in the new model.

PII and AOSI in relation to autism outcome

Based on the group differences identified in five out of the eight linear mixed effects models above for sensitive responsiveness, nondirectiveness, infant attentiveness, and mutuality, we tested whether these PII aspects predicted autism outcome (controlling for the effect of age and AOSI) to replicate previous findings and examine the predictive value of PII to ASD diagnosis. At 8 months, parent nondirectiveness and infant positive affect were significant predictors of autism outcome, irrespective of the addition of age and AOSI (nondirectiveness: $p = 0.02$; positive affect: $p = 0.001$; models 2 and 4, Block 3 in Table S5). The models were statistically significant (nondirectiveness: $\chi^2(3) = 9.033, p = 0.03$; positive

TABLE 2 linear mixed model analyses of PII between the TL and EL groups, controlling for infant age.

	Estimate	SE	df	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	95% CI
Sensitive responsiveness						
(Intercept)	3.31	0.30	241.12	11.18	<0.001	[2.73–3.89]
Age in months	0.11	0.02	136.64	5.89	<0.001	[0.08–0.15]
Group (EL-no autism)	−0.51	0.21	128.75	−2.49	<0.001	[−0.91–0.11]
Group (EL-autism)	−0.96	0.29	129.39	−3.28	<0.001	[−1.53–0.39]
Non-directiveness						
(Intercept)	4.05	0.30	242.47	13.71	<0.001	[3.47–4.63]
Age in months	0.05	0.02	142.02	2.67	<0.001	[0.01–0.09]
Group (EL-no autism)	−0.71	0.20	134.28	−3.53	<0.001	[−1.10–0.31]
Group (EL-autism)	−1.30	0.29	134.95	−4.54	<0.001	[−1.86–0.73]
Attentiveness						
(Intercept)	2.35	0.62	160.18	3.82	<0.001	[1.15–3.55]
Age in months	0.18	0.05	137.63	3.66	<0.001	[0.08–0.27]
Group (EL-no autism)	1.10	0.69	161.97	1.59	0.11	[−0.25–2.45]
Group (EL-autism)	2.34	0.97	153.75	2.42	0.02	[0.45–4.23]
Age: Group (EL-no autism) ^b	−0.10	0.05	138.82	−1.91	0.06	[−0.21–0.00]
Age: Group (EL-autism) ^b	−0.23	0.08	131.14	−2.86	0.004	[−0.38–0.07]
Liveliness ^a						
(Intercept)	2.17	0.32	173.03	6.83	<0.001	[1.55–2.80]
Age in months	0.25	0.03	149.27	9.78	<0.001	[0.20–0.30]
Positivity						
(Intercept)	2.07	0.89	160.21	2.34	0.02	[0.35–3.81]
Age in months	0.15	0.07	138.00	2.09	0.04	[0.00–0.28]
Group (EL-no autism)	−0.34	1.00	161.89	−0.34	0.74	[−2.29–1.60]
Group (EL-autism)	2.95	1.40	156.11	2.11	0.04	[0.22–5.67]
Age: Group (EL-no autism) ^b	0.05	0.08	139.41	0.67	0.51	[−0.10–0.21]
Age: Group (EL-autism) ^b	−0.18	0.11	135.40	−1.53	0.13	[−0.40–0.05]
Mutuality						
(Intercept)	3.49	0.31	235.66	11.35	<0.001	[2.89–4.09]
Age in months	0.08	0.02	139.89	3.71	<0.001	[0.04–0.12]
Group (EL-no autism)	−0.73	0.20	127.42	−3.61	<0.001	[−1.13–0.34]
Group (EL-autism)	−1.07	0.29	128.09	−3.72	<0.001	[−1.64–0.51]
Engagement intensity						
(Intercept)	3.15	0.26	174.88	12.22	<0.001	[2.64–3.65]
Age in months	0.10	0.02	152.47	4.83	<0.001	[0.06–0.14]

Note: As PII data were ordinal, analysis using cumulative link mixed models was also considered and performed, providing the same results as linear mixed effects models analysis. However, the latter was preferred due to ease of interpretation compared to the former, for consistency and comparability with the study replicated, and considering evidence suggesting that data with roughly distributed scores and >5 categories can provide less biased parameter estimates when treated as continuous than scores with less than 5 categories (Rhemtulla et al., 2012).

Abbreviations: CI, confidence interval.

^aUntransformed values for liveliness are reported as results using both transformed and untransformed values were similar.

^b· indicates group by age interaction.

affect: $\chi^2(3) = 15.410$, $p = 0.001$), explaining 13% and 22% (Nagelkerke R^2 : adjusted version of the Cox & Snell R -square) of the variance in autism outcome, respectively. Increasing nondirectiveness (or decreasing directiveness) was associated with reduced autism likelihood, with an odds ratio of 0.54 (95% CI [0.33–0.89]) and correctly classifying 87.1% of the cases. Positive affect was a

positive significant predictor, with increasing positivity being associated with an increased probability of autism diagnosis, correctly classifying 87.9% of cases.

At 14 months, borderline significant effects were found in the parent scales, and positive affect was a non-significant predictor of autism outcome. However, infant attentiveness to parent and dyadic mutuality significantly

FIGURE 1 Predicted values of the significant MACI scales by age and group (TL, EL-autism, and EL-no autism). This Figure illustrates the PII scales that differed significantly by group across 7–11 (8 months) and 13–18 (14 months). Infant attentiveness showed an age by group interaction. The scores on the Y axis range from 1 to 7 equating to minimal to high parent sensitive responsiveness, nondirectiveness, infant positive affect, attentiveness, and dyad mutuality, respectively. MACI, Manchester Assessment of Caregiver–Infant Interaction; PII, parent–infant interactions.

TABLE 3 Overview of the results.

	Group differences (8–14 months)	Autism outcome prediction (3 years)
Parent		
Sensitive responsiveness	Higher ratings in the TL than the EL groups (EL-no autism and EL-autism)	8 months: Nonsignificant predictor 14 months: lower parent sensitive responsiveness was related to autism outcome probability (borderline effect)
Nondirectiveness	Higher ratings in the TL than the EL groups (EL-no autism and EL-autism); higher ratings in the EL-no autism than the EL-autism group	8 months: higher directiveness at 8 months was related to autism outcome probability, controlling for age, AOSI and MSEL 14 months: lower parent nondirectiveness was related to autism outcome probability (borderline effect)
Infant		
Attentiveness	Group by age interaction: increasing scores for the TL group and decreasing for the EL groups between 8 and 14 months, with the lowest ratings in the EL-autism group	8 months: nonsignificant predictor 14 months: lower infant attentiveness was related to autism outcome probability—borderline effects after controlling for AOSI, further drop in effect size controlling for MSEL, no intervention effect
Positive affect	Group differences nonsignificant after pairwise comparisons test	8 months: higher positive affect was related to autism outcome probability, controlling for age, AOSI and MSEL 14 months: nonsignificant predictor
Negative affect	Not included in the model (see Supplementary Material)	Not tested
Liveliness	Nonsignificant group differences	Not tested
Dyad		
Mutuality	Higher ratings in the TL than the EL groups (EL-no autism and EL-autism)—controlling for the effect of intervention: those who underwent intervention at 14 months had lower scores in mutuality compared to the rest of the sample	8 months: nonsignificant predictor 14 months: lower mutuality was related to autism outcome probability—borderline effects after controlling for AOSI, further drop in effect size controlling for MSEL, no intervention effect
Engagement Intensity	Nonsignificant group differences	Not tested

Abbreviations: AOSI, Autism Observation Scale for Infants; MSEL, Mullen Scales of Early Learning.

predicted autism outcome ($p = 0.02$; models 8 and 10, Block 1 in Table S5). Increasing attentiveness to parent and mutuality were associated with decreased

probability of autism outcome. These domains dropped to marginally significant with the addition of AOSI (attentiveness: $p = 0.06$; mutuality: $p = 0.09$). AOSI

emerged as a significant predictor of autism outcome (models 8 and 10, Block 3 in Table S5).

The analysis was rerun including MSEL as a further predictor in the models to examine the variance infant developmental level accounted for in autism prediction, over and above PII, age and atypical behavior. At 8 months, there was no essential change in the results, with nondirectiveness and positive affect remaining significant predictors in the model. At 14 months, including MSEL led to a further drop in effect size for the otherwise marginally nonsignificant infant attentiveness and dyadic mutuality predictors (attentiveness: $B = -0.39$, $p = 0.20$; mutuality: $B = -0.26$, $p = 0.32$). Furthermore, including intervention as a further covariate (in addition to age and AOSI) at 14 months did not change the results of the main logistic regression analyses. Table 3 provides a brief description of all the results.

DISCUSSION

Examining early patterns of PII in relation to autism susceptibility and diagnosis is significant for a greater understanding of how autism develops. We aimed to test the replicability of previous findings by examining whether TL, EL-no autism, and EL-autism infant groups would differ in PII qualities through linear mixed models, and then conducted logistic regressions to test whether these qualities were associated with increased probability of 3-year autism classification. Regarding our first hypothesis, the current findings replicate Wan et al.'s (2013) observations for PII group differences at 8 and 14 months. EL-autism infants showed consistently lower parent sensitive responsiveness, parent nondirectiveness, and mutuality than the TL and EL-no autism groups. Interestingly, and in contrast to previous findings, infants at EL with a later autism diagnosis had higher scores on positive affect compared with the other groups, but that group difference did not survive correction for multiple comparisons. In addition, unlike previous findings, infant liveliness and dyadic engagement intensity did not show a group effect. Regarding our second hypothesis, consistent with Wan et al. (2013), lower infant attentiveness and mutuality at 14 months predicted autism outcome, which was consistent with previous reports (though showing a significant trend after controlling for AOSI). However, infant positive affect at 14 months did not emerge as a significant predictor, which is what was previously found.

Further, we made two novel findings, which extend Wan et al. (2013). First, TL infants showed increased attentiveness to the parent between 8 and 14 months, while EL-autism infants' decreased, and EL infants' remained stable. This divergence was not observed in the previous smaller sample of a similar age (Wan et al., 2013) and might reflect emerging infant social

attention difficulties affecting EL-autism infants' attentiveness to parent during PII. Second, infant positive affect and parent directiveness at 8 months predicted autism outcome at 3 years, independent of early atypicality and developmental level. Predictive PII effects within the first year were not observed in the previous study. Overall, the study's findings replicate some elements of previous reports and extend previous work to show that differences in PII in infants with later autism are apparent from as early as 8 months. This may have implications for the timing and focus of parent-mediated interventions.

This is the first prospective study to identify changes in parental interactive behavior (directiveness) in infants with later autism within the first year of life. While infants with higher AOSI scores had more directive parents, the directiveness effect persisted after controlling for AOSI and developmental level. Furthermore, while previous PII research using a sibling design could not discount the possibility that parents of EL infants may adopt a more directive parenting style due to already having an autistic (older) child, the current study found that directiveness distinguished EL groups by autism outcome. These findings are consistent with the interpretation that parents may adopt an active interaction style based on their expectations of infant play and their infant's social capacities, leading to more directive behaviors to engage their infants in social interactions. Similarly, mutuality and infant attentiveness to parent at 14 months were significant predictors of autism outcome. This finding reveals a change (decrement) in parent–infant mutuality and infant behavioral attention at 14, and not at 8 months, suggesting that differences are more pervasive with development in infants with a subsequent autism diagnosis. Overall, parental, infant, and dyadic interactional domains are affected in infants at EL for autism, which holds implications for socio-cognitive development (Shultz et al., 2018).

Infants at EL with a 3-year autism diagnosis surprisingly were rated as displaying higher positive affect during play interaction at 8 months, contradicting previous findings for lower positive affect as a predictor of later autism diagnosis (Filliter et al., 2015; Landa et al., 2013; Wan et al., 2013). The MACI infant positive affect scale is a highly sensitive scale that considers both the quantity and quality of positive affect. High positive affect might reflect developmental delays in EL-autism infants' social play such that they inclined toward more dyadic styles of play (without toys) or simpler toy play, which elicit moments of positive arousal (e.g., laughter in Peekaboo), while triadic styles of play (with toys) may involve deeper attention on toys and more sophisticated joint attention social skills (e.g., in book sharing). A second and perhaps related explanation is that high positivity may reflect infant temperament (refer to the [Supplementary Materials](#) for further discussion).

Limitations

Although the EL sample was one the largest to date in research investigating PII in autism susceptibility and diagnosis, the TL group was small. However, many of this group's PII ratings were similar to those by Wan et al. (2013) which employed a larger TL sample, or those by Whitehouse et al.'s (2019) baseline ratings. In addition, since EL and TL differences in PII were already much better established (Wan et al., 2019), our resources focused on coding PII in a large EL group. Measuring PII at only two time points prevented the observation of nonlinear effects in terms of how interactions unfold over time. It should also be acknowledged that, while the decision to control for AOSI was theoretically driven, this stringent approach may have led to some over-adjustment, resulting in a possible under-estimation of true group differences. The study design also does not allow for drawing causal inferences of the effect of infant interactive behavior on the parent, and vice versa, nor of early PII on autism diagnosis. Such causal effects can be inferred by controlled intervention studies—and trials that have focused precisely on the parental nondirectiveness as studied here—have indeed showed that increasing parent nondirectiveness is associated with later increased child attentiveness to parent and modified autistic trajectories (Green et al., 2017; Whitehouse et al., 2021), and a reduced level of autism diagnosis at 3 years (Whitehouse et al., 2021).

CLINICAL IMPLICATIONS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

By 8 months, parents of infants with later autism were more directive than parents of infants with no autism outcome. In the same group of infants, we have previously reported potential early brain function alterations in social attention in infants at EL-autism within the first year, suggesting the concurrent emergence of neural differences with differences in parent behavior (Elsabbagh et al., 2012; Tye et al., 2020). Preemptive interventions (e.g., iBASIS) that aim to support parents to follow a child's attentional focus have shown positive subsequent effects on social communication and autistic development (Green et al., 2017; Watson et al., 2017; Whitehouse et al., 2021). The present study suggests that beginning such interventions in even earlier development may be beneficial (Grzadzinski et al., 2021). Future longitudinal studies that can map longitudinal outcomes that include child well-being will be critical to address this question.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

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DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

ETHICS STATEMENT

The study obtained ethical approval from the NHS National Research Ethics Service (06/MRE02/73).

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

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